

JOURNAL

of the

MAYFLOWER STATE SENATE

at

THE REGULAR SESSION

Commenced at Lander on Sunday, March 9th, 2002, at 7:27 PM,
and adjourned on Sunday, March 9th, 2002, at 8:34 PM.

2002
Lander, MF

OFFICERS
of
MAYFLOWER STATE SENATE

DEVELOPINGNUBLETS.....President of the Senate
[VACANT].....President Pro Tempore
MECHANELIZE.....Chief Clerk
[VACANT].....Senate Parliamentarian
DOMIEISOK.....Sergeant-at-Arms

STAFF OF THE CLERK’S OFFICE:

STANLEY LABSON.....Journal Clerk
TRADEAFFECT.....Assistant Journal Clerk
ANTHONYSVIBING.....Clerk for Indexing

The Senate met on Sunday, March 9th, 2002, at 7:27 PM this day and was called to order by the President of the Senate.

ROLL CALL

- The roll was called and the following Senators answered to their names:

PRESENT	NOT PRESENT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ModernMcNoble • boosta_z • coolg6ry • turbanwarfare • kalani18 • kenneytube • sudonuII 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IvanKrizan • WooleyMcNoble • JamesMHamilton • mellyyeey • vincefant

- Senator mellyyeey makes herself present later into the session.
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EXECUTIVE NOMINATIONS AND BUSINESS

- Senator boosta_z motions to move to legislative business.
 - Objected to by Senator kalani18.
 - In the opinion of the Presiding Officer, the nays have it, and the motion fails.
- Senator kalani18 motions to discharge SGN035 from committee.
 - Seconded to by Senator sudonuII.
 - The motion passes by unanimous consent.
- Senator kalani18 motions to bring SGN035 to the floor.
 - Seconded to by Senator turbanwarfare.
 - The motion passes by unanimous consent.
- Senator mellyyeey makes herself present.

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5. Senator boosta_z motions to move to legislative business.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator kenneytube.
 - b. Objected to by Senator turbanwarfare.
 - c. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the nays have it, and the motion fails.
 6. Senator kalani18 motions to begin a voice vote on SGN035.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator sudonuII.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the ayes have it, and the nomination passes.
 7. Senator kalani18 motions to discharge SGN034 from committee.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator sudonuII.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
 8. Senator ModernMcNoble motions to table SGN034.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator kenneytube.
 - b. Objected to by Senator sudonuII.
 - c. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the nays have it, and the motion fails.
 9. Senator kalani18 motions to bring SGN034 to the floor.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator sudonuII.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
 10. Senator kalani18 requests three minutes to speak.
 - a. The Presiding Officer grants the request.
 11. Senator boosta_z motions to begin a voice vote on SGN034.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator turbanwarfare.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the ayes have it, and the nomination passes.
 12. Senator turbanwarfare motions to move to legislative business.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator kenneytube.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
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LEGISLATIVE RESOLUTIONS, BILLS, AND BUSINESS

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1. Senator boosta_z motions to bring SR032 to the floor and to begin a voice vote.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator sudonuII.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the nays have it, and the resolution fails.
2. Senator mellyyeey motions to bring SB132 to the floor.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator kalani18.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the nays have it, and the resolution fails.
3. Senator kenneytube motions to begin a voice vote on SB132
 - a. Seconded to by Senator mellyyeey.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the ayes have it, and the bill passes.
4. Senator boosta_z motions to bring SB127 to the floor and to begin a voice vote.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator mellyyeey.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the nays have it, and the bill fails.
5. Senator boosta_z motions to bring SB133 to the floor.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator coolg6ry.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the nays have it, and the resolution fails.
6. Senator boosta_z requests time to speak on the bill.
 - a. The Presiding Officer grants the request.
7. Senator boosta_z motions to begin a voice vote on SB133
 - a. Seconded to by Senator mellyyeey.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the nays have it, and the bill fails.
8. Senator kenneytube motions to discharge SB139 from committee.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator boosta_z.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
9. Senator kenneytube motions to discharge SB139 from committee.

- a. Seconded to by Senator boosta_z.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
10. Senator kenneytube motions to bring SB139 to the floor and to begin a voice vote.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator mellyyeey.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the ayes have it, and the bill passes.
11. Senator boosta_z motions to blanket discharge all proposed items from committee.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator ModernMcNoble.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
12. Senator coolg6ry motions to hold Senator boosta_z in contempt.
 - a. The Presiding Officer orders a 2 minute recess to review the standing rules.
 - b. Senator boosta_z is warned by the Presiding Officer, and Senator coolg6ry withdraws the motion.
13. Senator kenneytube motions to bring SB128 to the floor.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator boosta_z.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
14. Senator boosta_z motions to bring SB128 to the floor and to begin a voice vote.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator kenneytube.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the nays have it, and the bill fails.
15. Senator turbanwarfare motions to bring SB138 to the floor.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator boosta_z.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
16. Senator kenneytube motions to begin a voice vote on SB138.
 - a. Seconded to by Senator boosta_z.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the ayes have it, and the bill passes.
17. Senator boosta_z motions to bring SB122 to the floor and to begin a voice vote.

- a. Seconded to by Senator kenneytube.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the ayes have it, and the bill passes.
18. Senator kenneytube motions to bring all docket items to the floor and to begin a voice vote.
- a. Objected to by Senator turbanwarfare.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the nays have it, and the motion fails.
19. Senator turbanwarfare motions to table SB129.
- a. Seconded to by Senator sudonull.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
20. Senator ModernMcNoble motions to bring SB135 to the floor and to begin a voice vote.
- a. Seconded to by Senator kenneytube.
 - b. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the nays have it, and the bill fails.
21. Senator boosta_z motions to table SB136.
- a. Seconded to by Senator kenneytube.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
22. Senator turbanwarfare motions to begin a voice vote to consider all remaining docket items en bloc.
- a. Seconded to by Senator boosta_z.
 - b. The motion passes by unanimous consent.
 - c. A voice vote is held, in the opinion of the Presiding Officer the ayes have it, and the bills pass.
 - d. The following items were on the docket and being considered by this motion:

SB140 Flash Me Act	SB126 Contempt Authority Act
SB134 Miss Your Conduct Is Appalling Act	SB137 Round 'Em Up Act
SB130 Protect Our Skies Act	SB131 Not a Joke Act
SR030 Article V Amendment	SR031 ART. VII Amendment

23. Senator turbanwarfare motions to adjourn.
 - a. Seconded by Senator kenneytube
 - b. The motion prevails, with the senate adjourning on Sunday, March 9th, 2002, at 8:34 PM.

MECHANELIZE

/s/Mechanelize, Chief Clerk of the Senate